

Time Use in Complex Households: Detecting Subgroup Differences

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The collection of data based on time-use diaries has a deep history dating back to 19th century studies of the Russian peasantry. Official statistics agencies in high income countries now routinely collect data on time-use to gain insights into differences in sub-patterns of work and leisure across relevant social strata. The collection of time-use data in low-income countries is constrained by several well-known limitations of time-diary survey instruments; one of which is the inability to scale survey data collection for non/semi-literate populations. Building on prior work presented at the Joint Statistical Meeting, we continue to evaluate a new method of data collection that uses in-situ activity reporting. Our method results in discrete-time sampling of continuous-time activities and complicates traditional methods for detecting differences among sub groups. In this study we 1) describe a method for simulating complex, life-like activity structures, 2) propose an estimator to recover subgroup differences, and 3) evaluate the performance of the estimator over repeated simulations.

Key Words: Time Use, Microsimulation, Activity Simulation Algorithm (HASP), Sampling, Error Assessment, Performance

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1. Background

Scientific studies of human time-use date back to the ‘time-and-motion’ studies of human efficiency in factory settings of the late 1800s and more general studies of time-use in the Russian peasantry at the turn of the 20th century [1–6]. Today, sociologists, demographers, anthropologists, economists, scientific management professionals, public health professionals, and clinical psychologists continue to use time-use data to assess a range of human experiences from bargaining theory and feminist critiques, to addiction cravings, physical activity, and human mobility [6–14]. While each discipline draws on slightly different frameworks for time-use data collection, for official statistics the ‘time diary’ is the dominant method.

However, there are important limitations of time use diaries [5]. Time diary methods are limited in their ability to detect multiple simultaneous events (such as childcare and meal prep), artificial recall intervals (eg. 15 minute intervals), seasonal fluctuations in activity structures (such as school vacations), and coding detail (how minutely to code activities). These issues are exacerbated in low-resource environments, which also present additional challenges such as working with non- or semi-literate populations, costs of implementation, and sampling frames with regards to complex (multi-adult) cooperative households [5, 15].

In our prior work, we outlined a new method and sampling scheme aimed at improving existing methods for time-use data capture in these contexts [16]. Where many current time use studies [17, 18], rely on single-day time diaries and/or recall, our method uses a form of *in-situ* data collection, where participants are “alerted” or paged several times per day and asked to detail their current activity. Hence, instead of collecting a full day of activities, our method collects activities at a set number of samples per day across individuals. We further varied the structure of the activity alerts with a fixed sampler (activity collected at the same time each day across individuals) and a random sampler (activity collected at random times each day across individuals). Statistically, this introduces some additional complexity such as discrete-time sampling of activities occurring in continuous time, and a lack of closed-form solution for power/sample size calculations.

In this paper, we build from our prior work to assess the effectiveness of the in-situ method in a realistic but simulated environment. We aim to answer three research questions. Given our new audio-clip in-situ method, can this sampling approach provide estimates of group differences? What are the sample characteristics needed to attain sufficient power? Is there evidence of systematic bias in our results/estimates? To answer these questions we (1) propose a microsimulation algorithm to generate life-like activity structures with baked-in subgroup differences [19–24], (2) estimate differences across sub-groups using a logistic regression, and (3) assess the power, bias and error rates of the estimator across different sample sizes.

2. Microsimulation: Hierarchical Activity Structures

Microsimulation is an invaluable tool both conceptually and practically. Conceptually, microsimulation allows us to go from individual behavior to aggregate processes [19]. Practically, it allows us to simulate from a known truth which we can then use to benchmark performance. In our prior paper, we generated activity structures from multinomial distributions and Markov Chains, which we then used to assess the performance of the samplers. Though based in empirical data, these generation methods did not yield realistic day-to-day activity structures, and their noisy processes resulted in artificially high performance of the fixed sampler relative to the random sampler (see Figure 1, reproduced here).

Figure 1: Figure 1 shows an example of the underlying simulated activity structure using the multinomial generation approach (1a) and the Markov chain approach (1b) for thirty participants described above. Note the longer activity durations of the Markov chain approach, and the activity drift across time.

In this paper, we improve on these methods and introduce a hierarchical simulation method that generates a realistic simulation of day-to-day activities that has reasonable variation both day-to-day (within individual) and between groups (for example, gender) that we can model. Consistent with our prior work, we use pilot data to inform our microsimulation process. The pilot data comes from the Wearable Heart and Activity Monitoring (WHAM) study which collected time use diaries (written) as well as *in-situ* audio clip data from 17 undergraduate students for a two week period. We discretized time chunks into 48 half-hour periods and coded activities into six states: sleep, work, television, meals, personal care and other. From five days of data for two participants (non-weekend and habitual) we created a transition matrix of occurrence-exposure rates from origin activities ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 6$) to destination activities ($j = 1, 2, \dots, 6$) for each participant. Note that the i_j^{th} entry in the matrix is the probability of moving from state i to state j ($i \neq j$), or remaining in that state ($i = j$). The rows of this transition matrix are used in the simulation algorithm.¹

We approach simulating activity structures from a survival perspective, drawing on some of the considerable literature in survival analysis [20, 21, 23], multistate modeling [19, 24], and competing risk frameworks [22, 25]. Because we specifically wanted to generate realistic activity patterns (such as diurnal sleep and meal activities), we introduced a hierarchical component, and simulate sleep and meals across time and individuals first. To fill the gaps between sleep states and meal states, we use a competing risk framework that uses and scales the rows of the transition matrices from sleep or meal states to the remaining four states (tv, work, personal care, other). For the competing risk simulation, we take a cause-specific hazard approach and make several simplifying assumptions including proportional hazards, and a parametric, exponential, distribution. We draw heavily on Beyersman’s proposed process [24, 26, 27]. Drawing on Brilleman et al. and Crowther and Lambert’s work on clustered survival time simulation, our method leaves room for more detailed simulation of household effects (or groups within households such as ‘freshman’ or ‘eldest daughter’). In this preliminary work, we introduced one aspect of household clustering, but did not pursue a more nuanced approach. We outline the general process below²:

¹For the rest of the paper, we have repurposed the i^{th}, j^{th} notation.

²Code is included in the appendix.

2.1 Hierarchical Activity Simulation Procedure (HASP)

For a set number of sample individuals ($i = 1, \dots, n$), a set number of days ($d = 1, \dots, m$), and a set number of non-sleep, non-meal activities ($j = 1, \dots, s$)

1. Specify the hazard function as a Beta distribution and simulate sleep duration for each sample individual, i , and day, d , (T_{id}^{sleep})
2. Draw from a uniform distribution of sleep start times (9pm to 1am) clustered by household for each sample day
3. Draw from the exponential distribution the time to first meal after waking
4. Draw first meal duration from Beta distribution ($T_{id}^{\text{meal}_1}$)
5. Simulate time to second meal from Gompertz distribution
6. Draw second meal duration from Beta distribution ($T_{id}^{\text{meal}_2}$)
7. Simulate time to third meal from Gompertz distribution
8. Draw third meal duration from Beta distribution ($T_{id}^{\text{meal}_3}$)
 - If third meal start time is within 2-hours of next sleep time, disregard third meal
9. For the ‘sleep-to-first-meal’ gap: While $gap_{\text{meal}_1} > T_{id}$
 - Use sleep row of transition matrix and sample from exponential ($\lambda = \sum_{j \neq (\text{sleep}, \text{meal})} \pi_{\text{sleep}j}$) for T_{id}^j
 - Assign activity (from s) using a multinomial draw of activity probabilities scaled from transition row matrix
 - append T_{id}, T_{id}^j

Extend final activity to next meal state start
10. Repeat (9) and (10) using $\text{meal}_1, \text{meal}_2, \text{meal}_3$ rows of the transition matrices where gaps observed.

2.2 Results of Hierarchical Simulation

Using the simulation process described above, we generated two sub-group samples of 5 individuals in 200 households (1,000 individuals) per subgroup for a period of 30 days ($n_{\text{total}} = 2,000$). Two transition matrices with known differences were selected from the empirical data to form the basis of each subgroup. The complete sample (combined subgroups) we refer to as the enumerated data for clarity, and total activity differences are presented in Table 1 ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Figure 2 provides a visual assessment of the performance of the hierarchical activity simulation method. The diurnal structure of the sleep and meal onsets and durations are present and varying, as well as some amount of day-structured activities (such as the presence of TV predominantly in the evenings.) The two subgroups are also clearly very different, as Table 1 would suggest. Subgroup 1 spends considerable time working, whereas subgroup 2 spends a lot of time in “personal care”. (We consider these to be a “working student” population and an “American on vacation” population.)

We can further visually test the effectiveness of our simulation strategy using Kaplan-Meier survival curves. Displayed in Figure 3, sleep durations and meal onset occur as

(a) Hierarchical Activity Simulation Subgroup 1

(b) Hierarchical Activity Simulation Subgroup 2

Figure 2: Figure 2 shows an example of the underlying simulated activity structure for two days using the hierarchical activity simulation. The black vertical lines represent midnight (day reset), and ten “individuals” across 2 households are displayed. Note the regularity of sleep duration and onset by household, the regular meal times, and the change in activity based on time-of-day.

Table 1: Total Activities

Activity	Subgroup 1	Subgroup 2	Significance Flag	Obs. Difference ³
Meal	0.082	0.082	0	0
Other	0.106	0.066	1	0.041
Personal Care	0.042	0.289	1	-0.246
Sleep	0.347	0.346	0	0
TV	0.076	0.124	1	-0.048
Work	0.347	0.093	1	0.254
Sum	1	1		

expected. From the sleep curve, 50% of simulated individuals transition to their next activity after achieving 7 hours of sleep. None transition previous to 5 hours, and very few after 10 hours in the sleep state. From the meal occurrence or onset curves, similarly, by 8am 50% of simulated individuals have transitioned into their first meal (red), 50% by to their second meal by 1pm (green), and (if observed) 50% to their third meal by 7:15pm (grey).

3. Estimating Subgroup Differences

From our enumerated data, our aim was to test the ‘in-situ’ audio clip method against a known truth and to assess both performance of the method as well as power and sample size sensitivity. To accomplish this, we relied on estimates of subgroup differences from a logistic regression model and resampling approach, described below.

3.1 Statistical Estimation Approach

To estimate subgroup differences we fit a logistic regression model and assumed

$$Y_i \sim \text{Bernoulli}(\pi_i)$$

where

$$y_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } activity_i = activity_j \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

Then

$$\eta_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{subgroup}_1$$

and

$$g(\eta_i) = -\ln(1 + e^{\theta_i})$$

We clustered the errors by simulated individual (to account for individual dependence) and used sandwich estimators for standard error calculation [28, 29].

Using the enumerated data we resampled to create sets of fixed samples, random samples, and full samples as described in Table 2. We set the number of samples per day (t) at three, and the number of days included at 2. We sampled from each subgroup at 50, 100, 200, and 400 individuals per subgroup (total sample sizes of 100, 200, 400, and 800 respectively), and aggregated results over 500 simulations.

Sleep Durations

Meal Occurance

Figure 3: Figure 3 displays the Kaplan-Meier curves for sleep duration and meal onset. For sleep duration, 50% of simulated individuals transition to their next activity by 7 hours of sleep, though none transition previous to 5 hours, and very few after 10 hours in the sleep state. For the meal occurrence or onset, similarly, by 8am 50% of simulated individuals have transitioned into their first meal (green line), 50% by to their second meal by 1pm (red line), and (if observed) 50% to their third meal by 7:15pm (grey line).

Table 2: Resampling Procedure

Sampler Type	Daily No. (t)	Daily Times	Individuals (i)	Days (k)	Iterations
Fixed	3	7:30, 13:30, 19:30	100, 200, 400, 800	2	500
Random	3	random	100, 200, 400, 800	2	500
Full	NA	NA	100, 200, 400, 800	2	500

3.2 Resampling Results

To assess sampler performance, we estimate several quantities from the resampling procedure. First, we estimate the difference (d) between subgroups for each activity, calculate the 95% confidence intervals for each iteration, and flag a significant differences at $\alpha = 0.05$. From there we aggregate across all 500 simulations for each sample size and compare to the known difference (δ) from the enumerated data. We calculated the coverage (that is, how often the known difference falls within the calculated confidence interval), the Type I error rate (that is, how often the sample suggests that we reject the null hypothesis of no difference between groups even though there is not a known significant difference) and the Type II error rate (that is how often the sample suggests we should not reject the null, when there is a known difference). We do this for each sampler (fixed or random). We also keep a ‘full sample’ (which is the entire enumerated data for each of the two selected days) to provide an additional benchmark.

Table 3 shows the average point estimates of the difference in the proportion of time spent in each activity for each sample size and sampler method. For large known differences such as Work ($\delta = 0.254$), both the random and fixed sampler detect a sizeable difference between subgroups, though the fixed sampler inflates the difference. For small known differences such as TV ($\delta = -0.048$) the random and fixed sampler also detect the difference (on average), though again it appears the fixed sampler inflates the difference. For activities with no known difference such as Sleep ($\delta = 0$) the random sampler detects the lack of difference somewhat more consistently (and appears to converge faster) than the fixed sampler.

Table 4 provides and assessment of sampler performance with coverage and Type I and Type II error rates. Generally, the coverage for the random sampler is much better than the coverage for the fixed sampler. The Type I error rates are higher for the fixed sampler, and often exceed 0.05. The Type II error rates for both the random and fixed samplers are higher for smaller sample sizes of relatively rare activities such as TV and Other, but improve (as expected) with sample size. The Type II error rate is directly related to the Power ($1 - \beta$), and researchers generally aim for a Type II error rate less than 0.2 [30].

To round out the sampler performance, an assessment of bias is provided in Table 5. For the fixed sampler, there is evidence of bias; in particular for activities with large differences across subgroups such as Work and Personal Care, both of which inflate the difference. The random sampler appears to perform much better, converging to 0 as sample size increases. The mean error of the sample (that is the segmented enumerated data) is also biased, though, again, this converged towards minimal bias as sample size increases.

4. Discussion

In this paper, we aimed to assess the performance of a random and fixed ‘in-situ’ time use data collection method. To this end, we first described a procedure to simulate realistic activity structures with pre-determined sub-group differences rooted in empirical

Table 3: Detection of Subgroup Differences

Activity	Known δ	\bar{d}_{sample}	\bar{d}_{random}	\bar{d}_{fixed}	n
Meal	0.000	0.000	-0.001	0.001	100
		0.000	0.000	0.002	200
		0.000	0.001	0.002	400
		0.000	0.000	0.001	800
Other	0.041	0.039	0.039	0.056	100
		0.040	0.040	0.055	200
		0.040	0.041	0.056	400
		0.039	0.040	0.056	800
Personal Care	-0.246	-0.237	-0.247	-0.314	100
		-0.238	-0.246	-0.314	200
		-0.236	-0.248	-0.313	400
		-0.237	-0.247	-0.313	800
Sleep	0.000	0.000	0.004	-0.003	100
		0.000	0.002	-0.002	200
		0.000	0.001	-0.002	400
		0.000	0.001	-0.002	800
TV	-0.048	-0.047	-0.049	-0.062	100
		-0.047	-0.049	-0.062	200
		-0.047	-0.048	-0.063	400
		-0.047	-0.048	-0.062	800
Work	0.254	0.244	0.254	0.322	100
		0.246	0.253	0.321	200
		0.243	0.253	0.320	400
		0.245	0.254	0.320	800

Table 4: Sampler Performance: Coverage, Type I Error, Type II Error

Activity	n	Coverage			Type I Error		Type II Error	
		γ_{sample}	γ_{random}	γ_{fixed}	Random	Fixed	Random	Fixed
Meal	100	1.000	0.700	0.652	0.046	0.078	0.000	0.000
	200	1.000	0.672	0.696	0.050	0.044	0.000	0.000
	400	1.000	0.680	0.652	0.058	0.062	0.000	0.000
	800	1.000	0.642	0.706	0.044	0.068	0.000	0.000
Other*	100	1.000	0.754	0.608	0.000	0.000	0.606	0.424
	200	1.000	0.742	0.594	0.000	0.000	0.304	0.124
	400	1.000	0.732	0.432	0.000	0.000	0.044	0.006
	800	1.000	0.728	0.236	0.000	0.000	0.004	0.000
Personal Care*	100	0.980	1.000	0.946	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	200	0.938	1.000	0.698	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	400	0.916	1.000	0.182	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	800	0.928	1.000	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Sleep	100	1.000	0.920	0.672	0.000	0.078	0.000	0.000
	200	1.000	0.936	0.600	0.000	0.076	0.000	0.000
	400	1.000	0.922	0.598	0.000	0.098	0.000	0.000
	800	1.000	0.922	0.502	0.000	0.162	0.000	0.000
TV*	100	1.000	0.908	0.814	0.000	0.000	0.490	0.284
	200	1.000	0.920	0.738	0.000	0.000	0.180	0.064
	400	1.000	0.906	0.638	0.000	0.000	0.020	0.000
	800	1.000	0.892	0.466	0.000	0.000	0.002	0.000
Work*	100	1.000	0.766	0.146	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	200	0.938	0.764	0.020	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	400	0.916	0.732	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	800	0.928	0.774	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

Note: *Significant differences at $\alpha = 0.05$.

Table 5: Sampler Performance: Bias Assessment

Activity	n	Mean Error		
		ME_{sample}	ME_{random}	ME_{fixed}
Meal	100	0.000	0.001	-0.001
	200	0.000	0.000	-0.002
	400	0.000	0.000	-0.001
	800	0.000	0.000	-0.001
Other	100	0.002	0.001	-0.016
	200	0.001	0.000	-0.014
	400	0.001	-0.001	-0.015
	800	0.001	0.000	-0.015
Personal Care	100	-0.010	0.001	0.068
	200	-0.008	0.000	0.067
	400	-0.011	0.001	0.067
	800	-0.009	0.001	0.067
Sleep	100	0.000	-0.003	0.003
	200	0.001	-0.001	0.003
	400	0.001	0.000	0.002
	800	0.001	0.000	0.002
TV	100	-0.002	0.001	0.013
	200	-0.001	0.000	0.014
	400	-0.002	0.000	0.014
	800	-0.002	-0.001	0.014
Work	100	0.010	0.000	-0.068
	200	0.008	0.001	-0.067
	400	0.011	0.001	-0.066
	800	0.009	0.000	-0.066

data (HASP). From there, we proposed a simple logistic regression model to recover subgroup differences, and resampled from our enumerated simulation in accordance to our samplers. Finally, we aggregated results from 500 resampling iterations to assess estimator and method performance in terms of difference detection, power, error-type assessments, and bias.

Our results suggest that the random in-situ time-use data collection method may indeed be a feasible alternative to traditional time diary methods. The random method outperforms the fixed method in terms of detecting the true difference, coverage and error rates. Indeed it outperforms even the full sample method, which is equivalent to a perfect time diary, in terms of average difference estimation (if not coverage.) However, this method comes with important conceptual limitations. In particular, the assumption of sampling infrequently across a large body of individuals assumes that the broader group of individuals have observable characteristics that align with time use patterns. That is, in this simulation we assume subgroup (or household if we expand the simulation) completely aligns with differences in average time use. In a real-world setting, for some populations this assumption may hold (such as in highly gendered agrarian societies), but for broader populations this assumption may be inappropriate. Secondly, we did not assess *direct* point estimates of activity-proportion for each subgroup, and rather assessed *relative* differences. We suspect that a multinomial regression approach would be necessary to recover the exact differences in time use by subgroup, as the estimates from the logistic output will not sum to 1.⁴

Still, we believe that this method is promising for broader adoption in both low- and high-resource environments. Compared with traditional time diaries, this method is less burdensome, less costly, and feasible with large phone banks or texting platforms. Additionally, coupled with continuously monitoring technology (such as heart rate watches), more nuanced analyses are possible. The simulation method we propose here is also very flexible and it would be possible to tune to different underlying empirical data (such as previous time diary data). One could adjust household structures, clustering, number of activities, number of daily samples, and sample size. More advanced simulation may make implementation of this method less or more feasible depending on the complexity of the intended analysis.

5. Conclusion

In this paper we have assessed the performance of a novel in-situ audio clip method for time-use data collection. Given the positive performance of a random sampler implementation of the method, we believe that this method may provide a feasible alternative to traditional time use diaries, suitable for both high- and low-resource environments. While our results are limited by the specific tuning (and parameters) we chose for our simulated activity structure, we provide a very flexible Hierarchical Activity Simulation Procedure (HASP) that can be used to assess feasibility of complex activity structure designs and provide estimates of appropriate sample sizes to detect subgroup differences. We believe this method can help overcome traditional barriers to time-use data collection including participant burden (and attrition), costly implementation, and assumptions around participant resources / time structuring. Time-use studies provide important statistics for government agencies, non-governmental organizations, and policy makers. Given the widespread reliance on time use data, it is imperative we continue to update collection methods and assumptions.

⁴It also may be possible to scale the logistic point estimates and recover the underlying proportions, but the standard errors present more of a challenge. Authors have not yet investigated this.

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7. Appendix

Authors' code for Hierarchical Activity Simulation Procedure. Note that sleep, meals, and competing risk functions are coded separately and then incorporated into a larger function for general use.

```
# -----
# # Sleep # #
# -----

sleep_sim.f <- function(days, num_hh, ind_hh)
{
  ## Initialize for household level differences in duration
  num_hh <- num_hh
  num_ind <- ind_hh
  samplesize <- num_hh * ind_hh

  # Covariate Data
  covdat_sleep <- data.frame(id = 1:samplesize,
                             hh = rep(1:num_hh,each = num_ind),
                             sex = rep(c("M","F"),
                                       length.out=samplesize))

  # Betas
  betas <- c(shape1 = 20, shape2 = 18.2)

  # Hazard Function for Sleep
  haz_sleep.f <- function(t, x, betas)
  {
    res <- dbeta(x = (t/(1440+t)),shape1 = betas[1],shape2 = betas[2])
    res
  }

  # Simulate

  # Initialize
  # Survival Times
  d <- simsurv(betas = betas,
              x = covdat_sleep,
              hazard = haz_sleep.f,
              maxt = NULL,
              interval = c(1E-8, 100000))
  d_T <- d$eventtime
  # Start / stop
  # Cluster by household
  tstart_0 <- sample((-180:60)+1440*(0), size = num_hh, replace = T)
  tstart_0 <- rep(tstart_0,each = num_ind)
  tstart_0 <- tstart_0 + rnorm(samplesize, mean = 0, sd = 15)
  tstop_0 <- tstart_0+d_T
  # Data Frame
  iact = data.frame(id = 1:samplesize,
                   HH = covdat_sleep$hh,
                   sex = covdat_sleep$sex,
                   activity = "sleep",
                   tstart = tstart_0,
                   tstop=tstop_0,
                   event = 0)
```

```

for (i in 1:days)
{
  # Generate survival times
  d <- simsurv(betas = betas,
              x = covdat_sleep,
              hazard = haz_sleep.f,
              maxt = NULL,
              interval = c(1E-8, 100000))
  # Extract survival times
  d_T <- d$eventtime
  # Generate "start" times for sleep (Clustered)
  tstart <- sample((-180:60)+1440*i, size = num_hh, replace=T)
  tstart <- rep(tstart,each = num_ind)
  # Add noise
  tstart <- tstart + rnorm(samplesize, mean = 0, sd = 15)
  #Stop Time
  tstop <- tstart+d_T
  temp <- data.frame(id = 1:samplesize,
                    HH = covdat_sleep$hh,
                    sex = covdat_sleep$sex,
                    activity = "sleep",
                    tstart,
                    tstop,
                    event=i)
  iact <- rbind(iact,temp)
}
return(iact)
}

# -----
# # Meals # #
# -----

meal_sim.f <- function(days, num_hh, ind_hh, iact)
{
  num_hh <- num_hh
  num_ind <- ind_hh
  samplesize <- num_hh * num_ind

  # Initialize:
  # First Meal
  m1 <- simsurv(x=data.frame(id = 1:samplesize),
               dist = "exponential",
               lambdas = 0.05)
  m1_start <- ifelse(m1$eventtime<=1,0,m1$eventtime)+
               iact$tstop[iact$event==0]
  m1_end <- rbeta(n=num_hh, shape1=4, shape2=2)*60
  m1_end <- rep(m1_end,each = num_ind)
  m1_end <- m1_start + m1_end
  # Next Meal
  m2 <- simsurv(x=data.frame(id = 1:samplesize),
               dist = "gompertz",
               lambdas = .01,
               gammas = .8)
  m2_start <- m2$eventtime*60 + m1_end
  m2_end <- rbeta(samplesize,4,2)*60

```

```

m2_end <- m2_start+m2_end
# Third Meal
next_sleep <- iact %>%
  filter(event==0+1) %>%
  select(tstart)
m_num <- ifelse((next_sleep$tstart - m2_end) < 60, 0, 1)
m3 <- simsurv(x=data.frame(id = 1:samplesize),
              dist = "gompertz",
              lambdas = .01,
              gammas = .95)
m3_start <- m3$eventtime*60+m2_end
m3_start <- ifelse(m_num == 0, 0, m3_start)
m3_start <- ifelse(m3_start >= next_sleep$tstart,0,m3_start)
m3_end <- rbeta(n=samplesize,shapel = 4, shape2=2)
m3_end <- m3_end*60+m3_start
m3_end <- ifelse(m3_start == 0, 0, m3_end)
m3_end <- ifelse(m3_end >= next_sleep$tstart,
                next_sleep$tstart, m3_end)

# Bind it all together:
m <- iact %>%
  filter(event==0) %>%
  select(id, HH, sex, event)
meal1 <- m %>%
  mutate(tstart = m1_start,
         tstop = m1_end,
         activity = rep("Meal_1",samplesize))
meal2 <- m %>%
  mutate(tstart = m2_start,
         tstop = m2_end,
         activity = rep("Meal_2",samplesize))
meal3 <- m %>%
  mutate(tstart = m3_start,
         tstop = m3_end,
         activity = rep("Meal_3",samplesize))
m <- rbind(meal1,meal2,meal3)

# Simulate first meal:
for (i in 1:(days-1))
{
  # First Meal
  mm1 <- simsurv(x=data.frame(id = 1:samplesize),
                 dist = "exponential",
                 lambdas = 0.05)
  mm1_start <- ifelse(mm1$eventtime<=1,0,mm1$eventtime)+
    iact$tstop[iact$event==i]
  mm1_end <- rbeta(n=num_hh, shapel=4, shape2=2)*60
  mm1_end <- rep(mm1_end,each = num_ind)
  mm1_end <- mm1_start + mm1_end
  # Next Meal
  mm2 <- simsurv(x=data.frame(id = 1:samplesize),
                 dist = "gompertz",
                 lambdas = .01,
                 gammas = .8)
  mm2_start <- mm2$eventtime*60 + mm1_end
  mm2_end <- rbeta(samplesize,4,2)*60
  mm2_end <- mm2_start+mm2_end

```

```

# Third Meal
next_sleep <- iact %>%
  filter(event==i+1) %>%
  select(tstart)
mm_num <- ifelse((next_sleep$tstart - mm2_end) < 60, 0, 1)
mm3 <- simsurv(x=data.frame(id = 1:samplesize),
              dist = "gompertz",
              lambdas = .01,
              gammas = .95)
mm3_start <- mm3$eventtime*60+mm2_end
mm3_start <- ifelse(mm_num == 0, 0, mm3_start)
mm3_start <- ifelse(mm3_start >= next_sleep$tstart, 0, mm3_start)
mm3_end <- rbeta(n=samplesize,shapel = 4, shape2=2)
mm3_end <- mm3_end*60+mm3_start
mm3_end <- ifelse(mm3_start == 0, 0, mm3_end)
mm3_end <- ifelse(mm3_end >= next_sleep$tstart,
                 next_sleep$tstart,
                 mm3_end)

# Bind it all together:
m_ <- iact %>%
  filter(event==i) %>%
  select(id, HH, sex, event)
mmeal1 <- m_ %>%
  mutate(tstart = mm1_start,
         tstop = mm1_end,
         activity = rep("Meal_1",samplesize))
mmeal2 <- m_ %>%
  mutate(tstart = mm2_start,
         tstop = mm2_end,
         activity = rep("Meal_2",samplesize))
mmeal3 <- m_ %>%
  mutate(tstart = mm3_start,
         tstop = mm3_end,
         activity = rep("Meal_3",samplesize))
temp <- rbind(mmeal1,mmeal2,mmeal3)
m <- rbind(m,temp)
}
return(m)
}

# -----
# Competing Risks Function #
# -----

crisk.f <- function(group = 1, iact2, num_hh, ind_hh, days)
{
  num_hh <- num_hh
  num_ind <- ind_hh
  samplesize <- num_hh * num_ind
  ## Key
  key <- data.frame(id = 1:samplesize,
                   HH = rep(1:num_hh,each = num_ind),
                   sex = rep(c("M","F"),
                             length.out=samplesize))

  ## --- Identify gaps ----

```

```

# identify number of rows per person:
iact_2 <- iact2 %>%
  arrange(id,event,tstart)%>%
  filter(tstop!=0)
gap <- data.frame(NA)
gap_type <- data.frame(NA)
gap_start <- data.frame(NA)
r <- iact_2 %>% group_by(id) %>%
  summarize(n_id = n())
# iterate over number of rows
for (i in 1:samplesize){
  for (j in 2:r$n_id[i])
  {
    gap[i,j] <- iact_2$tstart[iact_2$id==i][j]-
      iact_2$tstop[iact_2$id==i][j-1]
    #coming from activity
    gap_type[i,j]<- iact_2$activity[iact_2$id==i][j-1]
    #stop of previous activity
    gap_start[i,j] <- iact_2$tstop[iact_2$id==i][j-1]
  }
}

# Collate Gaps and Transition Activities
gap <- data.frame(id = 1:samplesize,gap) %>%
  select(-NA.)%>%
  pivot_longer(cols = -id,
               names_to = "Gap_No",
               values_to = "Gap")
gap_type <- data.frame(id = 1:samplesize,gap_type) %>%
  select(-NA.)%>%
  pivot_longer(cols = -id,
               names_to = "Gap_No",
               values_to = "Activity")
gap_start <- data.frame(id=1:samplesize,gap_start) %>%
  select(-NA.) %>%
  pivot_longer(cols=-id,
               names_to = "Gap_No",
               values_to = "tstart")
gaps <- full_join(gap,gap_type)
gaps <- full_join(gaps,gap_start)
gaps <- gaps %>%
  filter(!is.na(Activity))

## --- Get the hazard rates for probabilities ---
# Read in transition matrices (this case, 2)
# Not going to use transition probabilities,
# instead use "period probabilities"
# that is, activities that occur between events:
# period 1: sleep and meal 1
# period 2: meal 1 and last meal
# period 3: meal 3 and sleep

TC_M_h <- as.matrix(TC_M[,2:5]) # Row 1 = Period 1,...
JE_M_h <- as.matrix(JE_M[,2:5]) # Row 1 = Period 1,...

if (group == 1)

```

```

{
  pmat <- TC_M_h
}
if (group == 2)
{
  pmat <- JE_M_h
}

## Simulate survival times and activity draws:
p1 <- p2 <- p3 <- data.frame(time = NA,
                             activity = NA,
                             id = NA,
                             tstart = NA)

for (i in 1:dim(gaps)[1])
{
  if(gaps$Activity[i]== "sleep")
  {
    m <- 0
    t <- 0
    while (m < gaps$Gap[i]){
      event.time <- rexp(1, sum(pmat[1,]))*60
      m = m + event.time
      t = append(t, event.time)
    }
    if(!is.na(t[2]) & t[2]<= gaps$Gap[i])
    {
      temp1 = data.frame(
        time=c(t[2:(length(t)-1)]),
        gaps$Gap[i]-sum(t[1:(length(t)-1)],na.rm=T)),
        activity = sample(c("other","pc","work","tv"),
                          size=length(t)-1,
                          replace=T,pmat[1,]),
        id = rep(gaps$id[i],length(t)-1)
      )%>%
      mutate(tstart = gaps$tstart[i]+cumsum(t[1:length(t)-1]))
      p1 = rbind(p1, temp1)
    }
    if(t[2]> gaps$Gap[i] | is.na(t[2]))
    {
      temp1 = data.frame(
        time = gaps$Gap[i],
        activity = sample(c("other","pc","work","tv"),
                          1,
                          replace = T,
                          pmat[1,]),
        id = gaps$id[i]
      )%>%
      mutate(tstart = gaps$tstart[i])
      p1 = rbind(p1, temp1)
    }
  }
  if(gaps$Activity[i]=="Meal_3")
  {
    m3 <- 0
    t3 <- 0
    while (m3 < gaps$Gap[i]){
      event.time3 <- rexp(1, sum(pmat[3,]))*60

```

```

    m3 = m3 + event.time3
    t3 = append(t3, event.time3)
  }
  if(!is.na(t3[2]) & t3[2]<= gaps$Gap[i] )
  {
    temp3 = data.frame(
      time=c(t3[2:(length(t3)-1)]),
      gaps$Gap[i]-sum(t3[1:(length(t3)-1)]),
      activity = sample(c("other","pc","work","tv"),
        size=length(t3)-1,
        replace=T,pmat[3,]),
      id = rep(gaps$id[i],length(t3)-1)
    )%>%
      mutate(tstart = gaps$tstart[i]+cumsum(t3[1:length(t3)-1]))
    p3 = rbind(p3,temp3)
  }
  if(t3[2] > gaps$Gap[i] | is.na(t3[2]))
  {
    temp3 = data.frame(
      time = gaps$Gap[i],
      activity = sample(c("other","pc","work","tv"),
        1,
        replace = T,
        pmat[3,]),
      id = gaps$id[i]
    )%>%
      mutate(tstart = gaps$tstart[i])
    p3 = rbind(p3,temp3)
  }
}
if(gaps$Activity[i]=="Meal_1" | gaps$Activity[i]== "Meal_2")
{
  m2 <- 0
  t2 <- 0
  while (m2 < gaps$Gap[i]){
    event.time2 <- rexp(1, sum(pmat[2,]))*60
    m2 = m2+event.time2
    t2 = append(t2, event.time2)
  }
  if(!is.na(t2[2]) & t2[2]<= gaps$Gap[i] )
  {
    temp2 = data.frame(
      time=c(t2[2:(length(t2)-1)]),
      gaps$Gap[i]-sum(t2[1:(length(t2)-1)],na.rm =T)),
      activity = sample(c("other","pc","work","tv"),
        size=length(t2)-1,
        replace=T,
        pmat[2,]),
      id = rep(gaps$id[i],length(t2)-1)
    )%>%
      mutate(tstart = gaps$tstart[i]+cumsum(t2[1:length(t2)-1]))
    p2 = rbind(p2, temp2)
  }
  if(t2[2] > gaps$Gap[i] | is.na(t2[2])){
    temp2 = data.frame(
      time = gaps$Gap[i],
      activity = sample(c("other","pc","work","tv"),

```

```

                                1,
                                replace = T,
                                pmat[2,]),
                                id = gaps$id[i]
                                )%>%
                                mutate(tstart = gaps$tstart[i])
                                p2 = rbind(p2, temp2)
                                }
                                }
                                }
                                res <- rbind(p1,p2,p3) %>%
                                #na.omit()%>%
                                mutate(tstop = tstart + time,
                                event = NA)%>%
                                select(id, tstart,tstop, activity, event)
                                res <- res %>%
                                left_join(.,key)
                                row.names(res) <- NULL
                                return(res)
                                }

                                # -----
                                # # Full Simulation Function # #
                                # -----

                                # -----
                                # # # Big Sim Function # # #
                                # -----

                                big_sim.f <- function(days, num_hh, ind_hh, group){
                                iact <- sleep_sim.f(days = days,
                                num_hh=num_hh,
                                ind_hh=ind_hh)
                                iact2 <- meal_sim.f(days = days,
                                num_hh=num_hh,
                                ind_hh=ind_hh,
                                iact = iact)
                                iact2 <- rbind(iact,iact2)
                                iact3 <- crisk.f(group = group,
                                iact2,
                                num_hh = num_hh,
                                ind_hh = ind_hh,
                                days = days)
                                iact_t <- rbind(iact2,iact3) %>%
                                filter(tstart != 0 & tstop != 0)
                                return(iact_t)
                                }

```

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